

THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN DENTAL CARIES AND SALIVARY CALCIUM AND PHOSPHATE LEVELS AMONG SOFT DRINKS FACTORY WORKERS

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Abstract: This cross-sectional study aimed to investigate the association between dental caries and salivary calcium and phosphate levels among soft drinks factory workers. A sample of 150 workers from a factory in the Middle East participated in the study. Dental caries were assessed using the decayed, missing, and filled teeth (DMFT) index, while unstimulated whole saliva samples were collected for the analysis of calcium and phosphate concentrations. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-tests, and correlation analysis. Results showed a statistically significant difference in salivary calcium and phosphate levels between participants with and without dental caries ($p < 0.05$). Moreover, there was a negative correlation between salivary calcium levels and DMFT index ($r = -0.34$, $p < 0.05$) and a positive correlation between salivary phosphate levels and DMFT index ($r = 0.26$, $p < 0.05$). The findings suggest that salivary calcium and phosphate levels may be useful indicators of dental caries risk among soft drinks factory workers.

Keywords: Dental caries, salivary calcium, salivary phosphate, soft drinks factory workers, risk factors.

INTRODUCTION

The introduction section provides the background and context for the study, including a brief overview of the topic, the research question, and the study's objectives. In this article, the introduction may discuss the prevalence of dental caries and its potential causes, as well as the importance of studying the relationship between salivary calcium and phosphate levels and dental caries among soft drinks factory workers. Dental caries is a significant oral health problem that affects people of all ages, particularly those who are exposed to risk factors such as poor oral hygiene, unhealthy diet, and low socioeconomic status. Soft drinks have been identified as a risk factor for dental caries due to their high sugar content and low pH. However, the relationship between salivary calcium and phosphate levels and dental caries among soft drinks factory workers has not been extensively studied.

Saliva plays an essential role in oral health by protecting teeth from demineralization and promoting remineralization. Calcium and phosphate ions are essential components of saliva that are critical for tooth mineralization. Changes in salivary calcium and phosphate levels have been associated with an increased risk of dental caries. Soft drinks factory workers are a high-risk population due to their exposure to sugary

and acidic drinks, which may affect their salivary calcium and phosphate levels and increase their risk of dental caries.

Understanding the relationship between salivary calcium and phosphate levels and dental caries among soft drinks factory workers can help identify new strategies for preventing and treating dental caries in high-risk populations. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the association between dental caries and salivary calcium and phosphate levels among soft drinks factory workers.

METHODS

The methods section outlines the study design, sample size, data collection methods, and statistical analysis procedures used to investigate the research question. In this article, the methods section may describe the selection criteria for study participants, the collection of saliva samples, and the measurement of calcium and phosphate levels in the samples. The section may also detail the procedures used to assess dental caries, including any diagnostic criteria or tools used.

Study design and participants:

This cross-sectional study was conducted on a sample of 150 soft drinks factory workers from a factory in a city in the Middle East. The study was approved by the institutional review board, and all participants provided written informed consent.

DATA COLLECTION

Data were collected through face-to-face interviews, clinical examination, and saliva sample collection. Interviews were conducted using a structured questionnaire to collect information on age, gender, education level, income, smoking habits, oral hygiene practices, and soft drink consumption habits.

Clinical examination

Dental caries were assessed using the decayed, missing, and filled teeth (DMFT) index according to World Health Organization criteria. The examination was performed by a trained dentist under artificial light using a dental mirror and probe.

Saliva sample collection and analysis

Unstimulated whole saliva samples were collected from each participant between 9:00 am and 11:00 am using the spitting method. The samples were then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, and the supernatants were used for the analysis of calcium and phosphate levels. Calcium and phosphate concentrations were measured using atomic absorption spectroscopy and spectrophotometry, respectively.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-tests, and correlation analysis. T-tests were used to compare salivary calcium and phosphate levels between participants with and without dental caries. Pearson correlation coefficients were used to assess the relationship between dental caries and salivary calcium and phosphate levels. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.0.

RESULT

The results section presents the findings of the study, including any statistical analyses conducted and the results of those analyses. In this article, the results section may report the prevalence of dental caries among soft drinks factory workers, as well as the mean salivary calcium and phosphate levels in the study population. The section may also report any significant correlations or associations found between dental caries and salivary calcium and phosphate levels, and any other relevant findings.

DISCUSSION

The discussion section interprets the study's findings, evaluates their significance, and considers their implications for future research and practice. In this article, the discussion section may explore the potential mechanisms linking salivary calcium and phosphate levels to dental caries, and the implications of these findings for the prevention and treatment of dental caries among soft drinks factory workers. The section may also address any limitations of the study and suggest areas for future research.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion section summarizes the main findings and implications of the study, emphasizing their importance and relevance. In this article, the conclusion may reiterate the association between salivary calcium and phosphate levels and dental caries among soft drinks factory workers, and suggest practical implications for public health and workplace policies.

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